

A Multi-Horizon Comparison of Machine Learning-Based Post-LOCA Forecasting Models

Kan Ni^{1&2,*}, Yonglin Zhu^{1&2}, Tianci Chen², Yimeng Zhao², Jason Hou³

¹IdeaS Research, Integrated Decisions & Systems Inc, Minneapolis, Minnesota;

²Advanced Analytics R&D, SAS Institute Inc, Cary, North Carolina;

³Department of Nuclear Engineering, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804134

ABSTRACT

Accurate prediction of Peak Cladding Temperature (PCT) during Loss of Coolant Accidents (LOCA) is essential for nuclear safety assessment and operator decision support. Traditional physics-based simulations require hours of computation, limiting their use for real-time applications during accident progression. This work presents a comprehensive benchmark of 25 time-series forecasting models for PCT prediction at 300- and 600-second horizons using 74 thermal-hydraulic features. The evaluated models include 12 Transformer variants, 3 convolutional neural networks (CNNs), 3 recurrent neural networks (RNNs), 4 multilayer perceptrons (MLPs), and 3 statistical baselines. The CNN-based SCINet achieved the best 300-second performance with a mean absolute error (MAE) of 10.91 °C (<1% relative error), while the Transformer-based Pyraformer achieved the best 600-second performance (MAE = 16.60°C), demonstrating the superiority of attention mechanisms for extended forecasting. Crossformer maintained consistent rank-3 performance across both horizons, showing robust multi-horizon generalization. Architecture family analysis indicates that CNNs excel at short-term forecasting through multi-resolution temporal modeling, Transformers dominate long-term horizons with advanced attention mechanisms, RNNs provide stable mid-tier performance, and statistical baselines remain competitive for short-term predictions. This dual-horizon benchmark establishes performance baselines and offers practical guidance for model selection in real-time nuclear safety applications.

Keywords: Loss of Coolant Accident, Peak Cladding Temperature, Transformer models, time series forecasting, multi-horizon prediction

1. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring nuclear reactor safety during Design Basis Accidents (DBAs) requires accurate prediction of critical safety parameters to support timely and informed operator actions. Among these scenarios, Loss of Coolant Accidents (LOCAs) are particularly safety-limiting, as breaches in the primary coolant system can lead to inadequate core cooling and subsequent fuel damage. Peak Cladding Temperature (PCT) serves as the key regulatory acceptance criterion, with a limit of 1204°C established by 10 CFR 50.46 [1].

Traditional safety analyses rely on system thermal-hydraulic codes such as RELAP5-3D and TRACE, which require hours of computation per scenario. This computational burden restricts their practicality for real-time applications such as control-room decision support and probabilistic risk assessments that demand thousands of scenario evaluations. Recent advances in deep learning for time-series forecasting have achieved remarkable success in domains such as weather prediction, energy load forecasting, and financial market analysis. In the nuclear field, machine learning for accident prediction has evolved from anomaly detection to time-series forecasting, with increasing adoption in non-safety-critical applications. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have demonstrated strong capability, achieving

*kan.ni@sas.com

over 95% accuracy and a $100,000\times$ speedup compared to RELAP5 simulations [2]. Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) variants such as the GRUS framework further improve performance through enhanced interpretability [3].

More recently, transformer architectures have emerged as the state of the art. Tohver *et al.* [4] achieved 30-second probabilistic forecasts, while Li *et al.* [5] applied the Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) to HPR1000 LOCA scenarios spanning 100–2000 seconds. Hybrid approaches combining Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), and attention mechanisms have also shown promise, as have Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) that embed conservation laws to improve generalization.

Despite these advances, no comprehensive investigation exists comparing modern architectures across forecasting horizons for nuclear accident prediction. This study addresses that gap by evaluating 25 time-series forecasting models for PCT prediction at 300- and 600-second horizons using 74 thermal-hydraulic features. The evaluated models include 12 Transformer variants, 3 CNNs, 3 RNNs, 4 multilayer perceptrons (MLPs), and 3 statistical baselines. We provide performance comparison, identify architecture-specific forecasting patterns, and offer practical guidance for model selection in real-time nuclear safety applications. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the problem formulation, datasets, and experimental design; Section 3 presents the results and discussion; and Section 4 summarizes key findings and outlines future research directions.

2. METHODS

2.1. Simulation Data Generation and Experimental Design

The nuclear accident scenarios used in this study are adopted from the open-source dataset provided by Qi *et al.* [6], which provides comprehensive time-series simulated data covering various Design Basis Accidents (DBAs) for Pressurized Water Reactors (PWR). All scenarios were generated using the RELAP5-3D thermal-hydraulic system code, which models a prototypical three-loop PWR with a rated thermal power of $3411 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$. The RELAP5 nodalization model incorporates detailed geometric and physical representations of major reactor components. Three reactor coolant loops are modeled with complete representations of hot legs, steam generators, cold legs, and reactor coolant pumps. Figure 1 illustrates the evolution of key thermal-hydraulic parameters during LOCA transients for two representative break severities (73% and 84% of hot leg cross-sectional area), showing the characteristic temporal progression of Peak Cladding Temperature (TPCT), Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS) flow rates (accumulator and high-pressure injection), and core water level. These transient profiles demonstrate the diverse accident progression patterns captured in the simulation dataset.

Figure 1. Evolution of key thermal-hydraulic parameters during a representative LOCA transient.

The 100 LOCA scenarios, representing break severities from 1 to 100 percent of hot leg cross-sectional area, were partitioned using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) with seed 42 to ensure representative severity distribution. The resulting split allocated 75 scenarios to training, 10 to validation, and 15 to testing. Additionally, 20 normal operation scenarios at power levels from 50 to 100 percent were included in the training set to ensure models learn both steady-state baseline behavior and accident-specific transient dynamics. The LHS methodology ensures test scenarios probe intermediate severity levels not directly represented in the training set. Figure 2 presents a Pearson correlation analysis demonstrating that normal operation and LOCA scenarios exhibit distinct feature relationship structures. The presence of these distinct correlation patterns benefits ML models by enabling them to establish a baseline for normal behavior during training.

Figure 2. Pearson correlation heatmap for representative parameters under normal operation and LOCA.

Table I summarizes the dataset composition and split configuration used in this study. A sliding-window approach with a stride of 1 was applied to extract overlapping temporal segments from each scenario time series, ensuring that each scenario produced multiple training samples while maintaining temporal coherence within scenario boundaries. This procedure yielded 24,378 training windows from 95 scenarios, 5,211 validation windows from 10 scenarios, and 5,528 test windows from 15 LOCA test scenarios.

Table I. Dataset composition and experimental split configuration

Scenario Type	Training	Validation	Testing
LOCA	75	10	15
Normal Operation	20	–	–
Total Scenarios	95	10	15
Total Samples	3,312	349	5,228

2.2. Problem Formulation

We formulate LOCA PCT forecasting as a multivariate time series prediction problem where the objective is to predict future PCT given historical observations of thermal-hydraulic state variables. Mathematically, given a historical observation window $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times D}$ of length L timesteps with D features, we seek to learn a function f parametrized by θ that predicts future PCT values $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times 1}$ for prediction horizon H :

$$\mathbf{Y}_{t+1:t+H} = f(\mathbf{X}_{t-L+1:t}; \theta). \quad (1)$$

For this investigation, we employ a lookback window of $L = 30$ timesteps corresponding to 300 seconds of historical context, dual prediction horizons of $H = 30$ timesteps (300 seconds ahead) and $H = 60$ timesteps (600 seconds ahead), a record interval of 10 seconds, and $D = 74$ thermal-hydraulic input features with target variable as PCT measured in Celsius. The 74 inputs included features span multiple physical domains: safety-critical parameters (RCS pressure, core water level, pressurizer level), thermal-hydraulic variables (hot/cold leg temperatures, coolant flows, steam generator pressures and levels), power indicators (thermal power, nuclear flux), safety system flows (high/low pressure injection, ECCS, accumulator), accident signatures (leak flow, containment pressure/temperature), and reactivity components (boron, moderator temperature, Doppler, control rods). From the original set of 85 simulation parameters, 11 were excluded to prevent data contamination: 3 fuel temperature variables (average fuel temperature TF, peak fuel temperature TFPK, submerged fuel temperature TFSB) not measurable by reactor instrumentation, and 8 severe-accident indicators representing core degradation phenomena—hydrogen generation from zirconium-water reaction (MH2), zirconium oxidation fraction (FRZR), corium/debris mass (MDBR), molten concrete mass (MCRT), core-concrete interaction gases (MGAS), and debris/concrete temperatures (TDBR, TSLP, TCRT), that are not measurable by reactor instrumentation during actual plant operation by internal results from RELAP5.

2.3. Time-Series Forecasting Model Selections

We evaluate 25 time-series forecasting architectures spanning four major model families, as summarized in Table II. Recent comprehensive surveys have reviewed the architectural diversity of deep learning approaches for time-series forecasting [7, 8], including focused analyses of Transformer-based methods [9]. Transformer architectures leverage a range of attention mechanisms that build upon the seminal framework introduced by Vaswani *et al.* [10]. CNNs exploit hierarchical feature extraction to capture multi-scale temporal dependencies. RNNs incorporate sequential inductive biases suited for dynamic state evolution. MLPs serve as lightweight alternatives to attention- and convolution-based models. Finally, classical statistical baselines (ARIMA, Moving Average, and Naive) provide lower-bound performance references for comparison.

Model implementations are adapted from the Time Series Library (TSLib) framework [8], with ARIMA, GRU, Moving Average, and Naive extended for comprehensive benchmarking.

2.4. Training Configuration and Evaluation Metrics

Table III summarizes the standardized training configuration employed across all models to ensure fair architectural comparison. Model-specific adjustments are applied only when architecturally required to accommodate unique design constraints.

Model-specific hyperparameters were adjusted only where required by architectural design. For example, TimesNet used `top_k = 5` and `num_kernels = 6` for period detection and temporal 2D-variation modeling. TimeMixer employed three down-sampling layers with a window size of 2 for multi-scale decomposition. SegRNN set the segment length to 30, matching the sequence length for optimal segment encoding. MICN required `label_len = seq_len` due to multi-scale convolution constraints. ETSformer adopted a symmetric encoder-decoder structure with equal layer counts for exponential-smoothing decomposition. These adjustments reflect inherent architectural requirements rather than manual hyperparameter tuning, thereby ensuring a fair comparison across model families.

¹Represents upper bound; early stopping with `patience=5` typically halted training at epochs 8–15 upon convergence.

Table II. Model architecture summary

Model	Family	Key Feature
Transformer	Trans	Standard encoder-decoder architecture with multi-head self-attention for capturing temporal dependencies
TFT	Trans	Variable selection network with gated residual units for interpretable multi-horizon forecasting
Nonstationary	Trans	De-stationary attention projecting queries and keys into stationary space using learnable statistics
PatchTST	Trans	Segments time series into semantic patches applying Transformer operations at patch level
Crossformer	Trans	Two-stage attention combining dimension-segment-wise and temporal attention for cross-dependencies
Pyraformer	Trans	Pyramidal attention modules for efficient modeling of temporal resolution hierarchies
Reformer	Trans	Locality-sensitive hashing attention reducing complexity from quadratic to log-linear
Informer	Trans	ProbSparse self-attention selecting dominant queries via KL-divergence for long sequences
iTransformer	Trans	Inverted paradigm applying attention on variates rather than temporal dimensions
FEDformer	Trans	Frequency enhanced decomposition using Fourier and wavelet transforms in frequency domain
Autoformer	Trans	Auto-correlation mechanisms identifying time delay aggregations with trend-seasonal decomposition
ETSformer	Trans	Exponential smoothing components combining level, trend, and seasonal terms with residuals
SCINet	CNN	Recursive downsample-convolve-interact architecture with multi-resolution temporal feature extraction
TimesNet	CNN	Converts 1D series to 2D tensors via FFT applying inception convolution
MICN	CNN	Multi-scale isometric convolution networks with downsampling and upsampling preserving sequence length
SegRNN	RNN	Segments sequences into fixed-length windows encoding each via RNN cells
LSTM	RNN	Long short-term memory with gating mechanisms including forget, input, and output gates
GRU	RNN	Gated recurrent units with simplified reset and update gates for efficient training
TimeMixer	MLP	MLP-Mixer with multi-scale temporal mixing and trend-seasonal decomposition
TSMixer	MLP	All-MLP architecture alternating time-mixing and feature-mixing layers
DLinear	MLP	Linear decomposition separating trend via moving average and remainder components
FreTS	MLP	Frequency domain model applying complex-valued transformations in Fourier space
ARIMA	Stats	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average with autoregressive and moving average components
Moving Average	Stats	Sliding window average over last N timesteps for simple trend-following
Naive	Stats	Persistence forecast repeating last observed value for all future horizons

Table III. Standardized Training Configuration

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
<i>Time Series Configuration</i>		<i>Training Setup</i>	
Sequence length	30 timesteps (300s)	Optimizer	Adam (weight decay 10^{-4})
Label length	15 timesteps (150s)	Learning rate	0.0005
Prediction horizon	30/60 timesteps (300s/600s ahead)	Batch size	32
Sampling interval	10 seconds	Maximum epochs	20^1
Input features	74	Early stopping patience	5 epochs
Target variable	PCT	Learning rate schedule	Cosine annealing
<i>Model Architecture</i>		Loss function	Mean Squared Error
Model dimension (d_{model})	128 (512 for iTransformer)	Gradient clipping	1.0
Feed-forward dim (d_{ff})	512	<i>Hardware Configuration</i>	
Encoder layers	2 (3 for iTransformer)	GPU	RTX 5080 16GB
Decoder layers	1	Docker image	nvidia/cuda:12.8.0-runtime-ubuntu22.04
Attention heads	4	Framework	PyTorch 2.12
Dropout rate	0.1	Training time/model	10–60 min
		Total budget	~200 GPU-hours

Evaluation employed the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) as the primary performance metric, defined as

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{NH} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{h=1}^H |y_{i,h} - \hat{y}_{i,h}|, \quad (2)$$

where N denotes the number of test samples, H the prediction horizon, $y_{i,h}$ the true PCT, and $\hat{y}_{i,h}$ the predicted PCT. MAE is selected for its interpretability, representing the direct temperature deviation in kelvins, and for its robustness to outliers compared with squared-error metrics.

Secondary metrics include the Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), defined as

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{NH} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{h=1}^H (y_{i,h} - \hat{y}_{i,h})^2, \quad \text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\text{MSE}}. \quad (3)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table IV presents comprehensive results for all 25 models at dual prediction horizons, with models ranked by MAE performance.

Table IV. Dual-horizon performance ranking

300s Ahead					600s Ahead				
Rk	Model	Arch	MAE (°C)	RMSE (°C)	Rk	Model	Arch	MAE (°C)	RMSE (°C)
1	SCINet	CNN	10.91	23.89	1	Pyraformer	Trans	16.60	22.69
2	TFT	Trans	12.43	26.34	2	Informer	Trans	18.67	24.58
3	Crossformer	Trans	12.75	18.76	3	Crossformer	Trans	19.11	25.47
4	Pyraformer	Trans	14.64	21.62	4	Transformer	Trans	19.18	26.61
5	LSTM	RNN	14.67	22.96	5	SCINet	CNN	21.53	37.75
6	GRU	RNN	14.90	23.70	6	TSMixer	MLP	21.69	29.11
7	Transformer	Trans	15.17	21.04	7	LSTM	RNN	28.45	37.33
8	Nonstationary	Trans	15.75	29.77	8	GRU	RNN	29.19	40.42
9	TimesNet	CNN	17.08	31.54	9	TFT	Trans	31.46	51.32
10	TSMixer	MLP	17.10	24.37	10	Nonstationary	Trans	36.41	57.98
11	TimeMixer	MLP	18.38	32.42	11	TimesNet	CNN	38.11	58.89
12	SegRNN	RNN	19.66	38.61	12	TimeMixer	MLP	39.03	59.71
13	Informer	Trans	19.92	27.31	13	SegRNN	RNN	46.95	72.44
14	ARIMA	Stats	20.88	50.82	14	Reformer	Trans	46.95	59.94
15	FreTS	MLP	20.99	34.40	15	FreTS	MLP	47.04	63.66
16	PatchTST	Trans	24.17	44.95	16	ARIMA	Stats	51.32	88.83
17	iTransformer	Trans	30.93	52.63	17	PatchTST	Trans	54.85	82.41
18	FEDformer	Trans	32.32	44.77	18	FEDformer	Trans	55.32	66.93
19	MICN	CNN	38.75	55.21	19	ETSformer	Trans	64.03	90.79
20	ETSformer	Trans	40.31	59.49	20	iTransformer	Trans	64.35	94.33
21	Naive	Stats	41.73	58.82	21	Naive	Stats	66.54	88.01
22	DLinear	MLP	44.67	66.71	22	MovingAverage	Stats	75.62	95.61
23	Reformer	Trans	49.54	68.34	23	DLinear	MLP	93.14	119.75
24	MovingAverage	Stats	51.70	69.50	24	MICN	CNN	115.60	143.28
25	Autoformer	Trans	60.08	89.36	25	Autoformer	Trans	161.82	195.33

Dual-horizon analysis reveals architecture-specific forecast capabilities. At 300-second horizon, SCINet achieves best performance with 10.91°C MAE representing sub-1 percent relative error. At 600-second horizon, Pyraformer achieves best performance with 16.60°C MAE, demonstrating Transformer superiority for long-term forecasting. Model rankings shift dramatically between horizons: SCINet excels at short-term prediction (rank 1 at 300s, rank 5 at 600s) while Pyraformer dominates long-term forecasting (rank 4 at 300s, rank 1 at 600s). Figure 3 illustrates SCINet and Pyraformer prediction performance for representative test scenarios. Crossformer maintains consistent rank-3 performance at both horizons, demonstrating robust multi-horizon capability. Three models achieve top-5 performance at both

horizons (Crossformer, SCINet, Pyraformer), establishing elite tier for production deployment across operational timescales.

Architecture family analysis reveals horizon-specific patterns. CNNs excel at short-term prediction by extracting features at multiple temporal scales simultaneously—capturing both rapid transients and slower trends—with SCINet achieving rank 1 at 300s. However, SCINet performance degrades for long-term forecasting (rank 5 at 600s) due to limited receptive field: convolutional operations process local temporal windows, restricting their ability to model dependencies extending beyond several hundred seconds into the future. Transformers demonstrate variable horizon dependency where sophisticated attention mechanisms (Pyraformer pyramidal attention, Crossformer cross-dimension attention) maintain strong performance across both horizons, while inappropriate inductive biases (Autoformer decomposition, Reformer LSH attention) fail catastrophically regardless of horizon. TFT achieves rank 2 at 300s through variable selection mechanisms though degrades to rank 9 at 600s. RNNs deliver robust mid-tier performance with LSTM and GRU achieving rank 5-6 at 300s and rank 7-8 at 600s, establishing recurrent processing as reliable for temporal evolution modeling. MLPs show horizon sensitivity, where TSMixer achieves competitive short-term performance (rank 10 at 300s), but degrades moderately at extended horizons (rank 6 at 600s). Statistical baselines maintain consistent relative performance with Moving Average achieving rank 24 at 300s and rank 22 at 600s, demonstrating limited horizon dependency for naive methods. For production deployment at 300s horizon prioritizing immediate accuracy, SCINet emerges as optimal choice. For 600s horizon requiring extended forecasting, Pyraformer provides superior performance. When multi-horizon deployment requirements dominate, Crossformer offers consistent rank-3 performance across both timescales. When interpretability requirements dominate, TFT provides strong short-term performance (rank 2 at 300s) with variable selection and attention visualization capabilities essential for regulatory acceptance.

Comparison with traditional methods further underscores the necessity of deep learning for achieving acceptable predictive accuracy. Statistical baselines such as moving Average and naive persistence exhibit 5–6× higher errors than the best-performing models. Conventional RNNs (LSTM, GRU) perform 25–34% worse than the leading Transformer and CNN architectures, though they remain viable for operational deployment.

Figure 3. Representative prediction performance comparing SCINet at 300-second horizon (top row) and Pyraformer at 600-second horizon (bottom row) for LOCA test scenarios.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents comprehensive benchmark evaluation of 25 time series forecasting models for LOCA PCT prediction at dual forecasting horizons (300-second and 600-second). Three models achieve top-5 performance at both horizons (Crossformer, SCINet, Pyraformer), establishing elite tier for multi-horizon deployment across operational timescales.

Future research will extend this benchmark along several critical directions currently under investigation. A multi-experiment framework will investigate the impact of training data composition, including pure LOCA baselines, cross-accident transfer learning from physically similar scenarios, and multi-accident diversity training to establish practical data curation strategies for practitioners. Hyperparameter optimization for top-performing models and multi-seed training with statistical testing will be investigated. Additional priorities include experimental validation through transfer learning from RELAP5 simulations to the LOCA experimental databases, as well as uncertainty quantification using Bayesian deep learning and conformal prediction approaches.

REFERENCES

- [1] US Nuclear Regulatory Commission. "Acceptance criteria for emergency core cooling systems for light-water nuclear power reactors." *Code of Federal Regulations, Title 10, Part 5046* (2022).
- [2] M. I. Radaideh, C. Pigg, and T. Kozlowski. "Neural-based time series forecasting of loss of coolant accidents in nuclear power plants." *Expert Systems with Applications*, **volume 160**, p. 113699 (2020).
- [3] Y. Fu, D. Zhang, Y. Xiao, Z. Wang, and H. Zhou. "An Interpretable Time Series Data Prediction Framework for Severe Accidents in Nuclear Power Plants." *Entropy*, **volume 25**(8) (2023). URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/25/8/1160>.
- [4] H. Tohver, A. Siirde, M. Sterner, and V. Kull. "Interpretable time series forecasting of NPP parameters in accident scenarios." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 398**, p. 111980 (2022).
- [5] X. Li, J. Xie, X. Zhao, Y. Liu, and M. Wang. "A long-term dependable and reliable method for reactor accident prognosis using temporal fusion transformer." *Frontiers in Nuclear Engineering*, **volume 3**, p. 1339457 (2024).
- [6] B. Qi, X. Xiao, J. Liang, J. Tong, P. Lei, F. Zhao, F. Si, H. Wang, W. Zeng, and X. Han. "An open time-series simulated dataset covering various accidents for nuclear power plants." *Scientific Data*, **volume 9**(766) (2022).
- [7] J. Kim, H. Kim, H. Kim, D. Lee, and S. Yoon. "A comprehensive survey of deep learning for time series forecasting: architectural diversity and open challenges." *Artificial Intelligence Review*, **volume 58**(216) (2025). URL <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10462-025-11223-9>.
- [8] Y. Wang, H. Wu, J. Dong, Y. Liu, C. Wang, M. Long, and J. Wang. "Deep Time Series Models: A Comprehensive Survey and Benchmark." *arXiv preprint arXiv:240713278* (2024). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.13278>. Code available at: <https://github.com/thuml/Time-Series-Library>.
- [9] Q. Wen, T. Zhou, C. Zhang, W. Chen, Z. Ma, J. Yan, and L. Sun. "Transformers in Time Series: A Survey." In *Proceedings of the Thirty-Second International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI-23)*, pp. 6778–6786 (2023). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.07125>.
- [10] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin. "Attention is all you need." In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 30, pp. 5998–6008 (2017).